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Scope of Sanskrit Studies in the Kerala Context

Dr. Shylaja S¹

Abstract

This paper explores the scope of Sanskrit research within the Kerala context, highlighting its profound influence on Malayalam and the Dravidian linguistic environment. Kerala's rich cultural tapestry, shaped by Aryan, Arabian, Portuguese, Jewish, Dutch, and British influences, has integrated Sanskrit deeply into its literary and linguistic fabric. Sanskrit's impact is visible in Malayalam phonology, morphology, syntax, and semantics, as well as in the literary traditions of Kerala, including classical poetry and drama. The study examines challenges in teaching Sanskrit as a second language, semantic shifts in Sanskrit-derived words, and the influence of Sanskrit literature on Malayalam. It underscores the need for comprehensive research to address these issues and enhance the relevance of Sanskrit in contemporary linguistic and literary studies.

Keywords: Sanskrit, Malayalam, linguistic influence, Dravidian languages, second language acquisition, semantic change, literary traditions, Kerala.

1.1 Introduction

Kerala is a land of diverse cultures. The Dravidian culture of Kerala has been influenced by Aryan, Arabian, Portuguese, Jewish, Dutch, and British cultures over time. This influence has led to the presence of Buddhism, Jainism, Saivism, Hinduism, Islam, and Christianity in Kerala, replacing the original Dravidian religion. The Aryan culture arrived from the north during the Ashoka period, bringing Buddhism with it to spread the teachings of Buddha. After the 6th century AD, Brahmanical culture began to spread in Kerala, along

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with the Sanskrit language. According to C. Rajendran, “The fifth and the sixth century witnessed the intrusion of the Kadamba kings to Kerala, which led to a fresh wave of Brahmin settlers to Kerala under the patronage of King *Mayuravrraman*, who is referred to in the Namboodiri traditions of *Keralotpatti*. By the eighth century, there came into existence the thirty-two Brahmin settlements which later on came to be the temple-cantered sites of Sanskritization” (01).

Just as the land of Kerala is rich in diverse cultures, the Malayalam language is closely intertwined with Sanskrit. The landlords and kings who followed Vedic rituals and power-centric systems in Kerala promoted the Vedic heritage and the Sanskrit language. This promotion played a major role in spreading Sanskrit among the common people, as they tended to imitate the culture of the powerful, such as kings, landlords, and those with high social status, reflecting the structure of society.

In 1867, the government established a book committee to prepare textbooks for schools, with *Kerala Varma Valiya Koyi Thampuran* as its chairman. He served in this role for a long time and prepared many textbooks in Malayalam, using a standardized version of the language that was more Sanskritized.

This is how Sanskrit became common in Kerala. There are two major aspects to this influence. The negative side is that the attitude towards the mother tongue and local culture shifted due to the dominance of Aryan culture. On the positive side, many Sanskrit texts on subjects like Ayurveda, astrology, literature, and architecture were well developed in Kerala. In this context, the study of Sanskrit is essential in the Kerala curriculum. From primary to secondary education, Sanskrit can be chosen as a second language. Beyond that, BA, MA, MPhil, and PhD programs in Sanskrit are offered by many colleges under universities in Kerala. Additionally, before the Four-Year Undergraduate Programme, both BA and MA programs in Malayalam language and literature include Sanskrit as a complementary paper. Consequently, the academic community well-versed in Sanskrit is very prominent in Kerala. Given this context, the scope of research in Sanskrit within Kerala is highly

relevant.

1.2 Review of Literature

There is considerable discussion on the scope of the Sanskrit language, but research specifically focused on 'the research scope of Sanskrit language in the Kerala scenario' is rare. In *Samskrutha Swadheenam Malayalaththil: Samkshipthapatanaavum Gaveshana Sadhyathaalum* (2016), K. Jayanisha delves into the influence of Prakrit and Sanskrit on Malayalam, particularly how Sanskrit loanwords have undergone semantic changes. She also examines the research scope and challenges of studying Sanskrit within the context of Malayalam, offering valuable insights for those interested in this intricate linguistic relationship.

Similarly, in *The Relevance and Scope of Sanskrit in the New Age* (2018), K. Unnikrishnan explores Sanskrit's enduring impact on Indian culture, emphasizing its influence on linguistic structures, global literary traditions, and spiritual heritage. He argues that, although Sanskrit is not widely spoken today, it remains a unifying force in India and continues to adapt to modern needs, serving as a timeless source of cultural, intellectual, and spiritual empowerment.

These two articles collectively highlight the general research scope in language and literature. This paper, however, aims to analyze the research scope of Sanskrit from a linguistic perspective in the Kerala scenario.

1.3 Linguistic and Literary Research Scope in Sanskrit Studies

In the context of the Malayalam environment and the Dravidian linguistic scenario, the scope of linguistic and literary research in Sanskrit is both rich and complex. Sanskrit, with its profound influence on Malayalam, offers a unique lens through which to explore linguistic features such as phonology, morphology, and semantics, as well as literary elements like poetic forms and thematic content. Understanding the convergence of Sanskrit with Dravidian languages provides valuable insights into language evolution, cultural exchange, and literary adaptation. This research delves into the impact of Sanskrit on Malayalam, identifying similarities and differences in linguistic structures and literary traditions, thereby

enriching our comprehension of both languages. The following topics are major areas of study to explore: the challenges of teaching Sanskrit as a second language in Kerala, the linguistic aspect of Sanskrit in Kerala, the influence of Sanskrit literature on Kerala's literary tradition, and the impact of Sanskrit on Malayalam language attitudes.

1.3.1 The Challenges of Teaching Sanskrit as A Second Language in Kerala

In Kerala, many students whose mother tongue is Malayalam opt to study Sanskrit as a second language in their school education. Despite the high marks students often achieve in Sanskrit, they struggle to speak it correctly and fluently, frequently making grammatical errors. This indicates a need to analyse and improve the methodologies used in teaching Sanskrit. Applying second language acquisition theories from applied linguistics could enhance these teaching methods.

A study of the problems faced by secondary school students in learning Sanskrit revealed several key issues. Many students find translating into Sanskrit challenging, while an average number of students reported difficulties in speaking pure Sanskrit. Additionally, students expressed a lack of interest in learning Sanskrit, finding the language difficult to understand, and Sanskrit grammar particularly hard to learn. The textbooks used were also found lacking in sufficient information related to Sanskrit grammar. The study suggested that grammar should be taught using more straightforward examples from everyday life and that teachers should provide more practice in reading, writing, and speaking Sanskrit in the classroom (Priti Chaudhari 281). This recommendation is applicable across India.

In the specific context of Kerala, where students' mother tongues are Dravidian languages, learning an Indo-Aryan language like Sanskrit presents unique challenges. A detailed case study could be conducted at different educational levels, including primary, upper primary, high schools, and higher secondary students. Furthermore, analysing language studies like Bachelor of Arts Programmes and Master of Arts Programmes in Sanskrit is crucial. Ideally, learning

a language should enable students to speak and write it proficiently. However, many students fail to achieve this competency. Therefore, focusing on the language learning environment, incorporating modern technology, and refining the curriculum framework to enhance language competency is essential.

The area of Second Language Acquisition (SLA) is one of the most critical research domains in the study of Sanskrit, particularly in the Kerala context. Traditional teaching methodologies need to be rigorously analysed to identify their limitations and develop more effective approaches for enhancing Sanskrit learning. In Kerala, this is especially important because while students are familiar with many Sanskrit words, they struggle with speaking and using the language fluently.

Researchers should focus on this area, as it holds significant potential for improving language instruction. More studies are needed to address these challenges, employing theories from applied linguistics and conducting case studies to gather empirical data. Questionnaires can be used to assess students' attitudes, difficulties, and learning preferences, providing valuable insights into the learning process.

For speakers of Dravidian languages, such as Malayalam, learning Indo-Aryan languages like Sanskrit can be particularly challenging due to the structural differences between the language families. Addressing this issue requires the development of efficient and tailored study materials for each educational level, ensuring that students receive the appropriate resources and support throughout their learning journey. By focusing on these aspects, scholars can contribute to creating more effective and accessible Sanskrit education in Kerala.

1.3.2 Linguistics Perspective

The phonological influence of Sanskrit on Malayalam is evident in the adoption of certain phonemes and pronunciation patterns. For example, Malayalam has incorporated retroflex sounds (*/b̠/*, */b̠ʱ/*, */d̠ʱ/*) from Sanskrit that were not originally present in the Dravidian phonetic inventory. This convergence is seen in how

certain Sanskrit-derived words are pronounced in Malayalam, often with a more palatalized or retroflexed articulation.

Morphologically, Malayalam has borrowed extensively from Sanskrit, especially in terms of prefixes, suffixes, and compound formation. For instance, the use of the suffix *-swar* in Malayalam, derived from Sanskrit *-svara*, demonstrates how Sanskrit morphological patterns have influenced Malayalam word formation. Additionally, many Sanskrit-based verb forms and grammatical structures are used in Malayalam, contributing to its complex morphological system.

The semantic shifts from Sanskrit to Malayalam provide a rich field for study. One notable example is the word *Kshethram*. In Sanskrit, *Kshethram* refers to a “place” or “field,” while in Malayalam, it has evolved to specifically mean temple. This shift reflects a significant change in meaning, influenced by the cultural and religious contexts in which the word was used. Such semantic changes often result from the integration of Sanskrit concepts into local practices and beliefs.

Syntactic convergence between Sanskrit and Malayalam is less direct but still significant. Malayalam syntax has been influenced by Sanskrit, especially in sentence structure and word order, notably in formal and literary contexts. For instance, the use of passive voice in Malayalam reflects the influence of Sanskrit syntax.

The pronunciation of Sanskrit-derived words in Malayalam has also undergone notable changes. For instance, the Sanskrit word *Sukham* (happiness) is pronounced as *Sukh* in Malayalam, reflecting phonological adaptation to local speech patterns. These changes are a result of the phonetic adjustments made by Malayalam speakers to integrate Sanskrit terms into their linguistic system.

Analysing these linguistic phenomena from a socio-linguistic perspective involves examining how social and cultural factors influence the adaptation and transformation of Sanskrit into Malayalam. For example, the semantic shift from *Kshethram* to “temple” can be understood in the context of Kerala’s religious and social practices, which emphasized the sacred nature of certain places.

The work of S. N. Sreedhar in 1989 on the Indo-Aryanization of Dravidian languages provides a foundational understanding of these linguistic interactions. Contemporary studies could build on this research by exploring how modern socio-cultural dynamics influence the convergence between Malayalam and Sanskrit. This analysis is not only valuable for understanding linguistic evolution but also has practical implications for AI and machine translation, where accurate representation of semantic and phonological nuances is crucial. Overall, the study of Sanskrit-Malayalam linguistic convergence offers insights into how languages influence each other over time, shaped by historical, cultural, and social contexts. This area of research continues to be relevant and offers opportunities for further exploration, particularly in the light of modern technological advancements.

All linguistic fields, particularly phonology, morphology, syntax, and semantics, require focused study of Sanskrit within the Malayalam language environment. Scholars should identify emerging trends in phonology, especially in the context of social media's influence, where certain dialect sounds become more common and gradually integrate into the standard phonological system. Morphologically, many Sanskrit words are Dravidianized to facilitate easier pronunciation, such as *Aparadam* becoming *Avaradam*.

These linguistic features need to be systematically identified and studied using sociolinguistic and dialectological methodologies. Understanding how social media and other modern influences shape language can provide valuable insights into the ongoing evolution of Malayalam in relation to its Sanskritic roots. The influence of Sanskrit on Sangam literature warrants thorough analysis, as it can provide insights into the historical and cultural interplay between these two linguistic traditions. Additionally, a comprehensive examination of the semantic changes of Sanskrit words in Malayalam is crucial. Many old Malayalam texts contain Sanskrit-derived words whose meanings have evolved significantly over time. This semantic shift can pose challenges in machine translation, where accurate

interpretation of these words is essential. Researchers should focus on analysing these semantic changes and understanding the reasons behind them. This involves investigating how and why the meanings of Sanskrit words have shifted in Malayalam contexts, considering factors such as cultural adaptation, regional usage, and historical developments. Scholars need to be meticulous and focused on these linguistic features within the Malayalam language environment. By addressing these semantic issues, researchers can improve the accuracy of machine translation systems and contribute to a deeper understanding of the linguistic dynamics between Sanskrit and Malayalam. Descriptive and comparative linguistic methodologies are well-suited for this type of research.

1.3.3 The Sanskrit Literature

The influence of Sanskrit literature on Kerala's literary tradition is profound and multifaceted, with *Manipravalam* serving as a prime example of this convergence. *Manipravalam*, a blend of Sanskrit and Malayalam, enriched medieval Kerala's literary landscape, evident in works like *Lilatilakam* and the *Ashtapadi* songs of the Geeta Govinda by Jayadeva. This fusion allowed poets to leverage the linguistic and aesthetic strengths of both languages, creating a unique literary style. Additionally, various literary forms in Kerala, including classical poetry, drama, and prose, were significantly shaped by Sanskrit. The impact of Sanskrit drama is particularly notable in Kerala's traditions of *Koodiyattam* and Kathakali, which incorporate Sanskrit aesthetics and themes. Classical poets such as Ezhuthachan and Cherusseri drew upon Sanskrit epics like the Mahabharata and Ramayana, reinterpreting these stories in a local context. While textual criticism has long been a part of studying these works, there remains a vast scope for contemporary analysis using modern literary theories. Approaches like feminist and postcolonial critiques could provide new insights, revealing the underlying social and cultural dynamics of the time.

Applying contemporary literary theories to medieval period works in Kerala can uncover the relationship between literature and

society. Romila Thapar's method in "Shakuntala: Texts, Readings, Histories," which examines how different versions of the Shakuntala story reflect their cultural and historical contexts, serves as an exemplary model. In Kerala, similar studies could analyse medieval works to understand the socio-cultural milieu of their production, exploring factors like the patronage system, the role of temples and religious institutions, and the influence of social hierarchies on literary output. This approach enhances our understanding of the works and sheds light on the societal structures of medieval Kerala.

The aesthetic sense and use of metaphor in Sanskrit-influenced Malayalam literature reflect the cultural richness of the period. Elaborate metaphors, a hallmark of Sanskrit poetry, are also present in Malayalam works. For instance, Cherusseri's "Krishna Gatha" is renowned for its vivid and intricate metaphors rooted in the Sanskrit tradition. Analyzing these elements can reveal the cultural and philosophical underpinnings of the literature, highlighting their artistic value. Contemporary literary discourse in Kerala actively discusses the application of modern theories to classical texts, including structuralism and post-structuralism, to uncover new dimensions of meaning. This approach revitalizes the study of Sanskrit's influence on Malayalam, making it relevant for modern readers and scholars. By incorporating contemporary literary theories and focusing on the socio-cultural context of medieval works, scholars can gain a deeper understanding of how these texts reflect and shape societal values, enhancing appreciation for Kerala's literary heritage and the dynamic interplay between language, literature, and society.

In the field of literature, it is essential to comparatively analyze various aspects of Sangam literature—including metaphors, ethics, Vedic culture, themes of love and passion, environmental descriptions, and poetic meter—against Malayalam literary traditions and Sanskrit literary traditions. This comparative study should aim to identify both similarities and differences in how these elements are treated across these literary cultures. Additionally, researchers should focus on contemporary Sanskrit literature,

particularly writings found on social media and other digital platforms. This modern corpus reflects the evolving nature of Sanskrit and its interactions with current societal contexts. Analyzing this contemporary literature can provide insights into how Sanskrit is being adapted and maintained in the digital age.

Researchers should apply relevant theoretical frameworks to their studies to ensure a thorough and nuanced understanding. Using appropriate literary theories will help in making sense of the comparative and contemporary analyses, ultimately contributing to the relevance of Sanskrit in modern contexts. This approach will enhance the appreciation of Sanskrit literature and its ongoing evolution, ensuring it remains a vibrant and contemporary field of study.

1.3.4 Language Attitude

Standardized Malayalam, often referred to as official Malayalam, is highly influenced by Sanskrit. This influence is evident not only in literary works but also in everyday language use. Official documents, circulars, and notices frequently employ Sanskrit-derived technical terms, which often fail to convey the intended meaning to the general public. This over-reliance on Sanskrit terminology can be attributed to a perceived prestige associated with Sanskrit, leading people to believe that its use lends authority and sophistication to their communication.

The long-standing power structures in Kerala have perpetuated this diffusion, as Sanskrit has historically been the language of the elite and scholarly classes. As a result, there has been a significant integration of Sanskrit into official Malayalam, creating a linguistic barrier for many common people who may not fully understand these terms. This situation underscores a broader issue: the need to critically examine the attitude towards Malayalam in its diffusion with Sanskrit. Without addressing this, there is a risk of alienating the broader population and gradually eroding the cultural essence of the language.

Studying these attitudes is crucial for the longevity and vitality of

Malayalam. By conducting comprehensive attitude studies through questionnaires targeted at students, government officials, and the general public, researchers can gain insights into how these groups perceive the use of Sanskrit in Malayalam. Such studies would involve understanding the perceived prestige of Sanskrit, the accessibility of Malayalam as a medium of communication, and the impact of these linguistic choices on cultural identity.

The results of these studies could inform the development of a nuanced language policy aimed at preserving and promoting Malayalam while acknowledging its historical ties with Sanskrit. This policy should strive to balance the use of Sanskrit-derived terms with more accessible Malayalam equivalents, ensuring that official communication is clear and inclusive. By addressing these issues through informed policy-making, it is possible to foster a linguistic environment where Malayalam thrives, maintaining its cultural integrity and ensuring its continued relevance in contemporary society.

1.4 Conclusion

In conclusion, the study highlights the significant impact of Sanskrit on the Malayalam language and its cultural milieu, emphasizing both the enriching contributions and the challenges posed by this linguistic convergence. The research identifies a crucial new area for exploration: the integration of modern linguistic methodologies, such as sociolinguistic and dialectological approaches, to address the evolving interactions between Sanskrit and Malayalam in contemporary settings. Unlike traditional peripheral literature studies, which often focus on historical or static analyses, this new research area emphasizes the dynamic nature of language evolution influenced by social media, educational practices, and modern communication technologies. By investigating these contemporary factors, scholars can gain deeper insights into the ongoing transformation of Malayalam in relation to its Sanskritic roots. This approach not only enhances our understanding of linguistic convergence but also provides practical implications for improving language education and translation systems, ensuring

that the rich heritage of both languages continues to thrive in a modern context.

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